

Funded by
the European Union

ESIRA — ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

Horizon Europe Grant agreement: 101136253

Author: Institute for Development and Innovation – IRI

REGIONAL REPORT ON SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND SOCIAL ECONOMY INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Jablanica and Pčinja Districts – Serbia

Project details

ACRONYM	ESIRA
Title	ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS
Grant Agreement Number	101136253
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2023-COMMUNITIES-01
Project Coordinator	UNIVERSIDAD DE BURGOS

Name of the region: Jablanica and Pčinja Districts

Country/NUTS-2 region: Serbia/Southern and Eastern Serbia

Territorial level: NUTS-3

Keywords	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social exclusion, - social economy, - social enterprises, - rural areas, - marginalisation, - Serbia.
-----------------	--

To cite this publication: Novković, N., Anđelković Đoković, M., Jevtović N. (2024) *Regional Report On Social Exclusion And Social Economy Initiatives In Rural Areas - Jablanica and Pčinja Districts – Serbia*, ESIRA project

Table of content

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Methodology	3
3. Country overview: Serbia	5
3.1 Territorial system of the country	5
3.2 Strategies and policies.....	6
3.3 Territorial inequalities in Serbia	9
3.4 Social economy.....	10
3.4.1 History and Evolution of the social economy.....	10
3.4.2 National strategies/framework to support the social economy.....	11
3.4.3 Types of social economy organizations.....	13
4. Regional overview – Jablanica and Pčinja Districts.....	15
4.1 Geographic and historical aspects	15
4.2 Demography.....	16
4.3 Economic situation	17
4.4 Institutional setting	20
4.5 Local policies and instruments	21
5. Vulnerability and Social Exclusion in the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts	23
5.1 Social exclusion and poverty	23
5.2 Labour market	25
5.3 Environmental vulnerability	26
5.4 Disadvantaged groups.....	27
5.4.1 Youth in NEET status	27
5.4.2 Women	27
5.4.3 Entrepreneurs.....	28
5.4.4 Roma people	28
5.5 Access to services.....	29
6. Assets and potentials in the region	29
6.1 Significance of developing the socio-economic potentials in the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts	31
7. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP	34
8. References.....	36
9. Partners	39

1. Introduction

The main aim of this report is to present the situation of rural areas and the communities residing in each of the participating regions in the ESIRA project (Enhancing Social Innovation in Rural Areas HORIZON 101136253). These reports will act as the basis of D4.1, “Benchmark study on social exclusion in rural areas,” and D4.2, “Multi-level analysis of social economy initiatives in rural areas”.

This report aimed to go beyond the literature and statistical data available and, together with the organisations participating in the pilots, explore the regions' situations and the drivers behind the disadvantages.

The report introduces the territorial organization of Serbia and analyses the situation of people living in rural areas, focusing on territorial inequalities.

A deeper examination of the drivers of vulnerability and social exclusion in rural contexts was done in Jablanica and Pčinja Districts. The analysis considers the social processes in the region and the livelihood opportunities at the municipal level. Existing assets and hidden resources in the municipality were assessed according to statistical data and the opinions of the leading local social economy stakeholders.

The development of a regional socio-economic report for the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts is essential for gaining a comprehensive understanding of the practical challenges faced by marginalized groups in these regions. This study aims to thoroughly examine the social and economic conditions and interpret the specific factors that can contribute to improving the position of individuals living in rural communities. By identifying unique barriers such as limited access to education, inadequate infrastructure, and high unemployment rates, the study seeks to provide a clear and detailed picture of the socio-economic landscape and the specific needs of marginalized groups, such as women, youth in NEET status, and entrepreneurs. Without such a detailed analysis, addressing these issues in a meaningful way would be challenging, as a deep understanding of the socio-economic context is crucial for developing effective and targeted solutions.

2. Methodology

The research methodology integrates both qualitative and quantitative research methods, with a particular emphasis on qualitative approaches. This dual-method framework was designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic conditions and development opportunities within the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts. The aim of the study was to go beyond existing literature and statistical data to explore the underlying drivers of disadvantage and identify potential pathways for improvement.

The report utilized quantitative methods to collect and analyze data from strategic planning documents across the 13 municipalities within the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts. This involved a thorough examination of documents to extract relevant information, which was essential for understanding the socio-economic landscape of the region.

Qualitative methods were a critical component of the study, designed to gain deeper insights into the socio-economic conditions and stakeholder perspectives. Qualitative (semi-) structured interviews were held with key stakeholders, including policymakers, administrators, and representatives of local Civil Society Organizations (CSO), to capture their views and experiences regarding the region's socio-economic environment.

For the development of the socio-economic report, a comprehensive set of data sources was utilized, including information from the National Statistical Office, local and national development strategies, academic articles and white and grey papers. National statistical data provided essential quantitative metrics on economic conditions, employment rates, and gender disparity levels, which formed the foundation for the study's analysis. In addition, strategic documents from both local municipalities and national agencies offered insights into developmental goals and policy frameworks that are relevant to the region. The study also drew on academic literature to integrate existing research findings and theoretical perspectives into the analysis.

Engaging in discussions with local stakeholders has been of paramount importance for understanding the problems faced by communities and building social capital for the future. Through these conversations, researchers gained valuable insights into the specific challenges, needs, and perspectives of residents, which are crucial for developing effective and contextually relevant solutions. Local stakeholders, including community leaders, residents, and local organizations, provide on-the-ground knowledge that complements broader socio-economic analyses and helps identify practical issues that may not be visible through secondary data alone.

3. Country overview: Serbia

3.1 Territorial system of the country

The administrative divisions of Serbia are regulated by several key legislative documents.

The Law on Territorial Organization (Zakon o teritorijalnoj organizaciji, 2007) prescribes the territorial organization of Serbia consisting of municipalities, cities and the City of Belgrade as capital city and autonomous provinces as a form of territorial autonomy. These territorial organizations are official administrative territorial units and exist as legal entities.

Republic of Serbia is divided into 174 local self-governments (LSG) each with the sovereign right to independently perform tasks within its jurisdiction without the influence of the national government. Municipalities are prescribed as basic organizational units for conducting local government that have more than 10,000 inhabitants. Cities represent another type of LSG with more than 100,000 inhabitants. There are 29 cities in Serbia, and 145 municipalities. The local self-government system in Serbia is uniform, meaning that all established LSGs and have the same status, structure, and almost identical competencies no matter the size of the LSG (Anđelković Đoković, 2024).

Table 1: Number of LSGs by Population Size

Population Size	Up to 5,000	5,001–10,000	10,001–20,000	20,001–50,000	50,001–100,000	100,000+	Total
Number of Municipalities	2	25	47	41	1	0	116
Number of Cities	0	0	0	6	9	13 (City of Belgrade over 1 million)	28
Total LSUs	2	25	47	47	10	13	144

Source: Anđelković Đoković, M. (2024). *Finalna analiza: Monitoring projekata i usluga podržanih kroz fond za MOS sa pregledom strukture finalnih korisnika gde je to primenljivo* [Final analysis: Monitoring of projects and services supported through the MOS fund with an overview of the structure of final beneficiaries where applicable]. Izveštaj pripremljen za Ministarstvo državne uprave i lokalne samouprave Republike Srbije u okviru projekta Lokalna samouprava za 21. vek, uz podršku Vlade Švajcarske.

The average LSG in Serbia has about 46,000 inhabitants (or around 35,000 excluding the City of Belgrade). Most LSGs have populations ranging from 10,000 to 50,000. Around one-fifth of municipalities (23%) have fewer than 10,000 inhabitants, while half of the cities (53%) have fewer than 100,000 inhabitants. The average number of inhabitants per LSG is significantly lower in Europe. For example, Spain has about 8,100 municipalities, most of which have fewer than 5,000 inhabitants. Finland has approximately 450 municipalities with an average population of about 12,000. Additionally, in Serbia, the difference between the smallest and largest LSG is substantial - ranging from about 1,000 inhabitants in Crna Trava to about 1.6 million in the City of Belgrade (Anđelković Đoković, 2024).

The Law on Territorial Organization (Zakon o teritorijalnoj organizaciji, 2007) also prescribes that Serbia comprises of two autonomous provinces (AP): Vojvodina and Kosovo and Metohija. Vojvodina, located in the north, enjoys significant administrative autonomy, including its own government and assembly, which allows for effective management of regional affairs. In contrast, Kosovo and Metohija, located in the south, unilaterally declared independence in 2008; however, Serbia continues to claim it as part of its sovereign territory, maintaining its status as an autonomous province within **Serbian Constitution** (Ustav Republike Srbije, 2006) Only these forms of territorial organization in Serbia have their formal jurisdiction and sovereign right to independently perform it on their territory.

Additionally, **The Law on State Administration** (Zakon o državnoj upravi, 2005) defines the concept of an administrative district that can be established for the purpose of performing state administration tasks outside the seat of a state administration body (usually situated in the City of Belgrade as capital city). An administrative district has an appointed manager, but it has no own jurisdiction (rights or obligations), they do not have their assemblies and present purely administrative entities organized under the 1992 government enactment. They are not legal entities. There are 29 such districts at the level of NUTS-3.

Finally, at the level of NUTS-2, but only for statistical purposes and administrative purposes, Serbia is divided into five NUTS-2 regions:

1. Vojvodina (matching the AP Vojvodina),
2. Belgrade,
3. Šumadija and Western Serbia,
4. Southern and Eastern Serbia,
5. and Kosovo and Metohija (matching the AP Kosovo and Metohija).

These regions are used in the **Law on Regional Development** (Zakon o ravnomernom regionalnom razvoju, 2009) where regions are established for the purposes of planning and implementing regional development policy. They are not an official administrative territorial unit of Serbia, and they are not legal entities.

3.2 Strategies and policies

The **Law on the Planning System in Serbia** (Zakon o planskom sistemu, 2018) regulates, among other things, the process of preparing, adopting, and implementing all public policies, as well as ensuring the mutual alignment of policies in the Republic of Serbia at all levels of government (national, provincial, and local). Public policies include strategies, programs, policy concepts, and action plans.

When it comes to regional development and policies that contribute to the development of rural areas in Serbia it is important to mention several strategies and policies. With this in regard we can probably divide all policies into two groups: a) the group of policies that are directly aimed to contribute to the balanced regional development or development of rural areas, b) the group of policies that can indirectly influence the rural development.

Observing the first group of policies that directly contribute to the balanced regional or rural development we can single out following policy documents:

- a) Above mentioned **Law on Regional Development** (Zakon o ravnomernom regionalnom razvoju, 2009), under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Economy in Serbia, among other things, establishes a methodology for determining the level of development of LSGs. Based on this methodology, all LSGs are classified into four groups: (1) LSGs with development levels above the national average; (2) LSGs with development levels ranging from 80% to 100% of the national average; (3) LSGs with development levels between 60% and 80% of the national average; and (4) LSGs with development levels below 60% of the national average. Within the fourth group, particularly vulnerable areas are identified as "devastated LSGs" which are defined as LSGs with development levels below 50% of the national average GDP per capita. This classification system is critical, as multiple support is designed and implemented based on these development categories.

Additionally, this Law establishes the National Development Agency and Regional Development agencies for each of five regions in Serbia as platforms for management of the Development Fund of the Republic of Serbia implements programs that encourage regional development through loans and grants.

This Law mandates the adoption of key strategic document including the National Strategy for Regional Development and regional plans for development of each region separately. National Strategy is still not adopted although its preparation started in 2023. Additionally, as previously mentioned, regions in Serbia are primarily "statistical units." However, the statistical region of Vojvodina overlaps with the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, which has its own administrative and political autonomy. Similarly, the Belgrade region coincides with the City of Belgrade, which operates as an autonomous LSG. Due to its unique circumstances, the Autonomous Province of Kosovo and Metohija cannot adopt any policy document. The remaining two regions, however, are purely statistical and lack the institutional capacity to independently adopt regional development plans without state intervention. This situation has further deepened the regional disparities, leaving the regions of Western Serbia and Šumadija, as well as Southern and Eastern Serbia, significantly less developed than the rest of the country (Mitic, 2024).

- b) On the other hand, AP Vojvodina and City of Belgrade have adopted their strategic development documents. **The Development Plan for the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina (2023-2030)** (Plan razvoja AP Vojvodina 2023-2030) aims to create a high standard of living by fostering sustainability, digital connectivity, and resilience. Its vision focuses on providing equal opportunities for work, promoting multiculturalism, and unlocking the full potential of citizens through quality education and services. The plan includes four main goals: 1) fostering micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises, innovation, and agricultural competitiveness; 2) developing an energy-sustainable, digitally connected Vojvodina; 3) creating a green Vojvodina resilient to climate change; and 4) building an intercultural environment that meets the needs

of its citizens. **The Development Strategy of Belgrade to 2027** (Strategija razvoja Grada Beograda do 2027.) envisions a city that is comfortable, competitive, safe, open, and sustainable. Key goals focus on creating a knowledge-based economy, ensuring financial stability, improving labor markets, fostering social inclusion, enhancing infrastructure, promoting healthy lifestyles, ensuring sustainable urban growth, and protecting the environment through circular economy practices and energy efficiency.

- c) The **Strategy for Sustainable Urban Development in Serbia up to 2030** (Strategija održivog urbanog razvoja Srbije do 2030. godine) emphasizes the importance of improving rural-urban connections and advocates for the inclusive local economic development, focusing also on better access to public services and digitalization. It is administered by the Ministry of Construction, Transportation and Infrastructure.
- d) Another significant policy regarding rural development was the the **National Rural Development Program** (Nacionalni program ruralnog razvoja 2022-2024) which provided financial support to improve agricultural productivity, diversify rural economies, and enhance rural infrastructure. Administered by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management, the program targets small and medium-sized agricultural enterprises, promoting modernization and competitiveness. Similarly, **Strategy for Agricultural and Rural Development 2014-2024**. (Strategija poljoprivrede i ruralnog razvoja Republike Srbije za period 2014-2024), administrated by the same Ministry, stressed agricultural and rural development based on knowledge, modern technologies, and standards, offering innovative products to both domestic and foreign markets. Although the strategic framework in the field of agriculture and rural development is expired there is the **Law on Agriculture and Rural Development** (Zakon o poljoprivredi i ruralnom razvoju, 2009) in place securing the funding for farmers. In 2025 around 1.3 bilion euros is budgeted for the farmers.

When it comes to the second group of policies that can indirectly influence the rural development, we single out following policy documents:

- a) **The Strategy for the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) for the Period 2023–2027** (Strategija razvoja malih i srednjih preduzeća za period 2023-2027) among other things emphasizes inclusive development by supporting women and youth entrepreneurs, especially in less developed areas. It highlights the need to create a supportive environment for women entrepreneurs, addressing regulatory challenges related to maternity leave and benefits. The strategy also calls for enhanced financial and non-financial support for young entrepreneurs, fostering innovation and access to essential infrastructure. By promoting inclusivity, the strategy aims to strengthen entrepreneurial initiatives and provide equal opportunities for underrepresented groups in Serbia's economic growth. It is administrated by the Ministry of Economy in Serbia.
- b) **The Employment Strategy of the Republic of Serbia (2021–2026)** (Strategija zapošljavanja u Republici Srbiji za 2021-2026) focuses on inclusive labor market policies, with special incentives for hard-to-employ groups such as women, youth under 30 (especially NEETs), persons with

disabilities, Roma, and others facing vulnerabilities like victims of domestic violence or human trafficking. It includes subsidies for self-employment, providing lump-sum grants for starting businesses and capacity-building for unemployed individuals. The strategy also encourages local governments to adopt employment action plans, subsidizing up to 70% of budgets for devastated areas.

- c) **The Tourism Development Strategy of Serbia (2016–2025)** (Strategija razvoja turizma Republike Srbije 2016-2025) among other things promotes rural development by emphasizing ethno-tourism and spa tourism as majority of these locations are in rural area. It also introduces a support system for entrepreneurs through incentive programs such as grants, infrastructure development, training, and digitalization initiatives to enhance the quality of rural tourism. Additionally, it encourages domestic tourism through voucher schemes and subsidized loans, fostering sustainable economic growth in rural communities. This holistic approach integrates local resources, improving the rural economy and creating opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises in tourism.

3.3 Territorial inequalities in Serbia

Identifying disadvantaged regions in Serbia involves recognizing specific areas that face substantial challenges in terms of economic development, infrastructure, and social well-being.

- Regions such as parts of Šumadija and Western Serbia (Parts of Kopaonik and Tara mountains) and Southern and Eastern Serbia (e.g., areas around Stara Planina and Golija) face geographical isolation and rugged terrain. These areas often have lower population densities and limited access to infrastructure and services due to their remote location.
- Peripheral and Border Areas: Regions near Kosovo and Metohija, particularly in municipalities like Priština, Peć, and Mitrovica, experience territorial disadvantages due to their proximity to sensitive border zones. These areas may face economic instability and security concerns stemming from historical and geopolitical factors.
- Flood-Prone Areas: Low-lying regions along rivers such as the Sava and the Danube, including parts of Vojvodina and Central Serbia, are vulnerable to flooding, which poses risks to infrastructure, agriculture, and local economies. These areas require specific measures for flood protection and sustainable land use planning.
- Industrial Decline Zones: Former industrial centres, including parts of Central Serbia such as Bor and Smederevo, have experienced economic decline due to the restructuring of industries. These regions struggle with high unemployment rates and the need for economic diversification.

Based on the Regional Strategy for Rural Development of the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts (2013), the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts are considered disadvantaged due to a combination of socio-economic and infrastructural challenges. Firstly, these regions suffer from high unemployment rates, particularly among youth and marginalized groups, which hampers economic growth and development. The lack

of industrial and business infrastructure further exacerbates this issue, as there are limited opportunities for investment and industrial expansion.

Moreover, the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts have inadequate transportation and communication infrastructure, making it difficult to attract businesses and investors.

Agricultural practices, a primary economic activity in these regions, are often underdeveloped and lack modernization, leading to lower productivity and income. Moreover, there is a significant outmigration of young and skilled individuals seeking better opportunities elsewhere, further depleting the local talent pool. The combination of these factors—economic stagnation, poor infrastructure, inadequate services, and outmigration—creates a cycle of disadvantage that is difficult to break without targeted interventions and comprehensive development strategies.

According to the Law on Regional Development, in Serbia, 19 municipalities and cities are considered devastated areas, where the level of development is below 50% of the national average. These devastated municipalities include Babušnica, Bela Palanka, Bojnik, Bosilegrad, Bujanovac, Vladičin Han, Golubac, Žitorađa, Kuršumlija, Lebane, Mali Zvornik, Medveđa, Merošina, Preševo, Prijepolje, Svrlijig, Surdulica, Trgovište, and Tutin. Nine of them are from the Jablanica and Pčinja districts.

More detailed data you can find in the sections that follow.

3.4 Social economy

3.4.1 History and Evolution of the social economy

In Serbia the social economy has its roots in the period of socialism when cooperatives and workers' self-management formed the foundation of the economic system. In the former Yugoslavia, workers' self-management enabled employees to participate in decision-making processes and share profits, fostering a more inclusive economic environment. Following the transition to a market economy in the 1990s, cooperatives and workers' self-managed firms underwent a transformation and adaptation to new conditions.

Prior to the 2022 when the Law on Social Entrepreneurship (Zakon o socijalnom preduzetništvu, 2022) was adopted in Serbia, neither social economy nor social entrepreneurship was defined as terms in Serbian regulations, and there was no legal basis for any public funds to be set aside on any level of government in Serbia.

However, even with the unfavourable legal, economic and institutional framework, social entrepreneurship did exist in Serbia. It appeared in the form of individual initiatives or relatively organized sub-sectors (e.g., enterprises for professional rehabilitation and employment of persons with disability) which solve the problems of unemployment and social exclusion. According to the results of mapping social enterprises in Serbia which was done in 2007 (Cvejic, Babovic, Vukovic, 2008), there were 1,160 of these enterprises in total and they employed around 0.5% of the total number of employees in Serbia.

The first network of social enterprises, SENS (Social Economy Network Serbia) was founded in 2011.

The SENS has been established with the aim to provide space for social enterprises to learn one from

another, to stimulate cooperation among social enterprises, as well as with other players, to ensure that social enterprises' products/services are found in one place so that they are easily browsed and accessible to potential buyers and partners for cooperation (Vukmirović, 2014).

A major role in the promotion of social entrepreneurship, as well as in the creation of a favourable environment for business operations and survival of social enterprises is played by the Social Inclusion and Poverty Reduction Unit of the Government of the Republic of Serbia (SIPRU). The team deserves the credit for bringing the idea of social entrepreneurship closer to the Government's bodies, for setting off initiatives for amendments and supplements to the laws that relate to social entrepreneurship and for linking together different sectors in the Government of the Republic of Serbia when it comes to the issues related to the development of social entrepreneurship (Vukmirović, 2014).

3.4.2 National strategies/framework to support the social economy

In 2022, the **Law on Social Entrepreneurship** (Zakon o socijalnom preduzetništvu, 2022) was adopted in Serbia, with the aim of creating a favorable environment for the development of social entrepreneurship, raising awareness about the importance of social economy and social entrepreneurship, and thereby meeting the social needs of a specific part of the population.

This Law defines **social economy** as an economy whose primary goal is to achieve benefits for the broader community and socially sensitive groups, rather than generating profit, while **social entrepreneurship** is defined as carrying out activities of general interest to create new and innovative opportunities for solving social problems, problems of individuals or socially sensitive groups, and preventing or eliminating the consequences of social exclusion, strengthening social cohesion, and addressing other issues in local communities and society as a whole.

The Law defines that the Republic, the province, and local self-governments can promote social economy through their policies in accordance with the Law on the Planning System, which stipulates that public policy documents be adopted by the assembly of the relevant authority after conducting a public discussion. It is also provided that the Government of the Republic of Serbia adopts a Program to Promote Social Entrepreneurship, which would, among other things, support and motivate other levels of government in Serbia to introduce incentives for the development of social economy/social entrepreneurship.

However, even two years after the adoption of the Law, the Program has not been adopted, and no local self-government has developed its own local strategic documents in this area. The Ministry of Employment has started to prepare the Program expected to be adopted in 2020.

The analysis of the current situation, which was prepared for the purpose of drafting the Program¹, highlights the following problems that affect the further development of the social economy:

¹ Draft of the Program is not publically available but it was submitted to the institute for review for the purposes of this analysis.

- a) Entities operating under the principles of social economy do not recognize themselves as such (self-recognition problem) having in mind that social economy in Serbia have not been promoted in several decades as vehicle to local development.
- b) Decision-makers don't recognize social enterprises as entities that can contribute to the growth of the local economy. Although some policies support social enterprises, they mostly do so indirectly, primarily by directing assistance towards socially vulnerable citizens not towards the social enterprise as such.
- c) Insufficiently developed forms of financing, meaning these enterprises primarily rely on donor funding. In Serbia, borrowing from any entity other than a commercial bank is prohibited, so microfinancing and loans from private funds are not allowed. Some banks have had programs aimed at developing social enterprises, but these were time-limited and do not represent systemic support for development.
- d) Related laws are not stimulative for the development of social enterprises. For example, the Public Procurement Law does not recognize special criteria for evaluating the offers of social enterprises, considering that it primarily promotes the lowest price as the evaluation criterion, which social enterprises find difficult to achieve (since their business model is not based on maximizing productivity and competitiveness).

LSGs have in the past recognized the importance of social entrepreneurship and have supported it in various ways, from participating in the establishment of social enterprises (e.g., the Social Enterprise "Radanska ruža" in Lebane) to providing space for social enterprises to operate (e.g., the Youth Center of the "Zaječarska Inicijativa") (Ministry of Labour, 2024). However, this support has not been systematic, but rather individual cases that other social enterprises cannot rely on. The support from local self-governments has primarily been linked to specific projects funded by international donors, considering that municipalities, prior to the adoption of the Law in 2022, had almost no means to support social entrepreneurship.

Often this support was linked to employment of hard-to-employ individuals, as outlined in the **Employment Strategy 2021-2026** (above mentioned), or it was linked to the support of socially vulnerable groups through strategies such as the:

- **Strategy for Social Inclusion of Roma (2022–2030)** (Strategija za socijalno uključivanje Roma i Romkinja za period 2022-2030),
- **Strategy for Improving the Status of Persons with Disabilities (2020–2024)** (Strategija za poboljšanje statusa osoba sa invaliditetom za period 2020-2024),
- **Strategy for Deinstitutionalization and Development of Community Social Protection Services (2022–2026)** (Strategija za deinstitutionalizaciju i razvoj usluga socijalne zaštite u zajednica za pirod 2022-2026).

In other words, in the absence of a universal definition of the social economy, institutions have largely associated it with addressing the needs of socially vulnerable groups not recognizing the potential of the social economy sector for fostering local economic development. These support measures have

primarily been framed as a component of social protection rather than as a broader driver of economic innovation and growth (NALED, 2025).

Having this in mind, as a result, only 20 social enterprises have been registered in Serbia, although it is estimated that there are between 200 and 500 enterprises operating on the principles of social economy (NALED, 2024).

3.4.3 Types of social economy organizations

Under the Serbian **Law on Social Entrepreneurship** (Zakon o socijalnom preduzetništvu, 2022), entities eligible to obtain social entrepreneurship status include entrepreneurs, legal business entities, and civil sector organizations registered for economic activities. These entities must fulfill at least one prescribed social role and allocate a minimum of 50% of their profits toward community development or activities benefiting vulnerable groups. Additionally, they are required to submit a biennial report detailing the fulfillment of their social mission.

As mentioned only around 20 social enterprises have been registered in Serbia up to the end of 2024 (NALED, 2024).

Observing in more detail, traditionally, in Serbia these legal forms often have some characteristics of social economy:

- **Cooperatives:** Serbia has a long tradition of cooperatives. According to the [Law on Cooperatives \(2015\)](#) (Zakon o zadrugama, 2015) there are several types of cooperatives, including agricultural, consumer, and worker cooperatives. As of most recent data for 2020, there are over 2,000 active cooperatives in Serbia, with the majority being agricultural with around 5,500 employees (Ministry of Economy, 2022).
- **Foundations:** Foundations in Serbia are usually established for philanthropic purposes, supporting education, culture, health, and social services by funding projects, organizing campaign funds, offering scholarships, providing resources, and assisting organizations in these areas. [The Law on Endowments and Foundations \(2010\)](#) (Zakon o fondacijama i zadužbinama, 2010) regulates these entities. There are 1.088 registered foundations in Serbia based on the official data of Business Registry for the 2024.
- **Associations (civil society):** Associations are the most common form of non-profit organizations in Serbia. [The Law on Associations \(2009\)](#) (Zakon o udruženjima, 2009) regulates these entities, which operate across various sectors, including social services, culture, and sports. There are over 37,000 registered associations in Serbia based on official data from Business Agency in 2024. In 2020. (the last official data) CSO engaged only 8.712 employees in 17.852 registered associations (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2022).²

² Note: This data does not mean that all of them are operating under the principles of social economy!

According to Tešić and Radetić (2023) enterprises operating in rural areas in Serbia, particularly in regions like Jablanica and Pčinja, are primarily focused on sectors that address the needs of local communities. These sectors include agriculture, rural tourism, and traditional crafts. Social enterprises in these areas often work on sustainable agricultural practices, the processing of local agricultural products, and the promotion of rural tourism by leveraging natural and cultural resources.

Example of social enterprise in Jablanica District

Name of the organization: Radanska ruža

Website <https://www.radanskaruza.rs/>

Address St. Nikole Tesle 18, Lebane, Serbia

Legal form: limited liability company

Sector of activity: Processing and preserving of fruits and vegetables

Geographical area of operation and its main characteristics: The food producing if localized in Lebane, but it employs women from Jablanica district. These women are producing home-made and handmade traditional fruit products and then finds market from them. They have established online market space.

Main target group(s): Women from rural area of Lebane and Jablanica district

Main challenges tackled: Employment of women in middle age (45-55) who are considered vulnerable in the labour market. In these rural areas these women are often inactive in labour market and more focused on unpaid household labour. Radanska Ruža also employs single mothers, as well as retirees who need additional income for living.

Contribution to local development and social inclusion: Having in mind that Lebane faces with high unemployment rates, especially for women, Radanska ruža have found the way to employ this group of citizens that is hard to employ but at the same time doesn't have a lot of skills necessary for modern, digital, workforce. These women are mainly focused on managing the household therefore Radanska ruža used the skills that they already have in producing food and helped them to make profit out of it.

4. Regional overview – Jablanica and Pčinja Districts

4.1 Geographic and historical aspects

Jablanica and Pčinja Districts hold a unique historical significance in Serbia due to their roles as border territories. Throughout history, these areas have been at the crossroads of various political, cultural, and economic influences, which have shaped their distinct identity and development. Jablanica and Pčinja have historically been situated on the frontier between different empires and states, including the Ottoman Empire and the Kingdom of Serbia. The historical significance of these districts is evident in the numerous fortifications, historical sites, and cultural heritage that reflect their role in regional power struggles and territorial disputes.

Moreover, the border position of Jablanica and Pčinja has fostered a rich cultural diversity influenced by various ethnic and religious groups. The presence of different communities, including Serbs, Albanians and Roma, has created a melting pot of traditions, languages, and customs.

Figure 1. Administrative districts of Serbia with Jablanica and Pčinja districts in the far south of Serbia

Source: <https://create.vista.com/vectors/serbia-map-map/>

The settlements are administratively divided into a total of 13 municipalities, covering a total area of 6,290 km², approximately 7% of the territory of the Republic of Serbia (Statistical Office, 2023).

Table 2: Overview of geographic characteristics of Jablanica and Pčinja

District	Number of LSGs	Surface in km ²	Number of settlements	Number of urban settlements
Jablanica district	6	2770	336	7
Pčinja district	7	3520	363	6

Source: Statistical Office of Serbia, 2023

According to the Regional Spatial Plan of the municipalities of Southern Pomoravlje (Regionalni prostorni plan opština Južnog Pomoravlja, 2010), the relief of Jablanica and Pčinja Districts is characterized by mountains and valleys. One of the characteristics and values of the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts, as rural areas, is their preserved nature. Of particular importance for the biological diversity of this region is its geodiversity - gorges, canyons, specific river valleys, as well as marshy and wet habitats and mountain bogs (Vlasina bogs on Vardenik and Čemernik), which are potential and proven centres of endemism and relictness in the Republic of Serbia. The flora and fauna represent a significant economic potential of this area, serving equally as a basis for tourism and scientific activities, and for the promotion of environmental protection and quality, both nationally and internationally, as well as for the well-being of the local population and visitors in health and aesthetic terms.

4.2 Demography

According to the last Population Census in 2022, Jablanica and Pčinja Districts have a population of nearly 380,000 people, constituting 6% of the country's total population. Leskovac, the administrative centre of Jablanica District, has the highest population with 124,000 residents, followed by Vranje, the administrative centre of Pčinja District, with 74,000 residents. The least populated municipality is Crna Trava with approximately 1,063 inhabitants (Official Statistics, 2022 Population Census).

Table 3: Overview of demographic characteristics of Jablanica and Pčinja

District	Population	Population in rural areas	Average age	Population 65+	Adult population (18+)	Youth (15-29)
Jablanica district	184,502	54%	44	22%	83%	16%
Pčinja district	193,802	56%	42	18%	81%	19%

Source: Statistical Office of Serbia, 2022, Population Census

The Jablanica District is characterized by a trend of depopulation. According to the census data, in Jablanica district the population decreased from 240,923 in 2002 to 184,502 in 2022. In Pčinja district, population decreased from 227,690 in 2002 to 193,802 in 2022.³

4.3 Economic situation

The Jablanica and Pcinja Districts, as part of the Southern and Eastern Serbia regional unit, are among the poorest areas in the Republic of Serbia observing main economic indicators.

As mentioned, the **Law on Regional Development** (Zakon o ravnomernom regionalnom razvoju, 2009), under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Economy in Serbia, among other things, lists all LSGs based on their level of development. The classification of LSGs is carried out based on the value of GDP per capita in the LSG compared to the national. There are 19 LSGs currently characterized as devastated areas, 15 of them are from the region of South and East Serbia and seven of them are in the Jablanica and Pčinja districts:

- Bojnik, Lebane, Medveđa in Jablanica District
- Bosilegrad, Bujanovac, Vladičin Han, Preševo, Surdulica, Trgovište in Pčinja District

Unfortunately, not a lot of economic indicators are officially available at the Statistical Office of Serbia. Some that are available show the unfavorable situation of the Jablanica and Pčinj districts. As shown in the table, while registered employment rates⁴ are the same (27%), registered unemployment is significantly higher in Jablanica and Pčinja (14% vs. 8%), and average wages are lower (470 EUR vs. 524 EUR). Investment in construction and fixed assets is considerably less in Jablanica and Pčinja, indicating underdevelopment. Even though these regions have a higher number of registered businesses and entrepreneurs per 1,000 citizens (75 vs. 53), majority of them are self-employed individuals (83% vs. 71%) that belong to the vulnerable employment by definition.

³ Although part of the Albanian population boycotted the census.

⁴ Share of registered employment in population. This is not comparable to the data from the Labour Force Survey but it is the only data available at the local level.

Table 4: Overview of main indicators, 2022, Jablanica and Pčinja district vs rest of the Serbia

Labor Market Indicators 2022			Investment Indicators 2022		
Indicator	Jablanica and Pčinja LSGs average	Rest of the Serbia average	Indicator	Jablanica and Pčinja LSGs average	Rest of the Serbia average
Registered employment rate as share in population	27%	27%	Construction value per capita	40,661 RSD (348 EUR)	78,165 RSD (668 EUR)
Registered unemployment rate as share in population	14%	8%	Investment in fixed assets value per capita	38,204 RSD (326 EUR)	102,791 RSD (879 EUR)
Average net wage	55,025 RSD (470 EUR)	61,352 RSD (524 EUR)	The number of registered businesses and entrepreneurs per 1000 citizens	75 (83% self-employed)	53 (71% self-employed)

Source: Author calculation based on Statistic Office data and Business Registry data

Approximately 55% of the total territory of the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts is under agricultural land (351,611 hectares), of which 80% is privately owned. The agrarian structure of the area is very fragmented, as farms with more than 3 hectares of total cultivated land are rarely found, even in mountainous regions (Agricultural Census 2023). Out of the 13 municipalities in these Districts, 10 fall into the category of areas with difficult agricultural conditions (Ministry of Agriculture, 2022). Agricultural production in southern Serbia is quite traditional. The influence of new technologies is limited either by small-scale production or by the lack of a connection between new knowledge and users. The problem is not the small number of people engaged in agricultural production, but the predominance of elderly farmers who are mostly not motivated to invest in the development and improvement of agricultural production. In terms of total agricultural land and its usage, the Jablanica District has more favourable conditions for agricultural production development compared to the Pčinja District. The city of Leskovac stands out, particularly regarding agroecological potential.

Although there are agricultural cooperatives and associations they are not at a satisfactory level of development. For example, the Development Plan of the City of Leskovac 2023-2029 and the Development Plan of the City of Vranje 2021-2030 recognize the necessity of strengthening the process of associating farmers with the aim of improving the capacity that will ensure the placement of produced products on the market as one of the priorities that they will also support through their measures.

The results of conducted interviews show that, craftsmanship represents a significant potential of this region and a quality option for diversifying the rural economy, although traditional crafts like cobbling are declining due to craftsmen shifting towards modern market demands (e.g., cobbling turning into general shoemaking). Currently, the most prevalent crafts are related to the maintenance and repair of automobiles, trucks, tractors, and other agricultural machinery, crafts in the construction sector (stonemasons, bricklayers, plasterers, carpenters, etc.). Also represented are services for repairing household appliances, white goods, computers, and similar items, as well as hospitality providers, bakers, confectioners, sheet metal workers, metal turners, foundry workers, photographers, and shoemakers. Modern crafts present in the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts are mainly oriented towards the needs of the local population. However, there is untapped potential, especially within tourism, for enhancing and developing traditional crafts and handmade products.

Besides their role in preserving the tradition of the Serbian people, traditional crafts can also contribute to improving gender equality in the region through promoting female entrepreneurship. The Tourist Organizations of the municipalities of Lebane and Bojnik actively promote the development of traditional crafts through events such as *Exhibitions of Traditional Crafts*. The Tourist Organization of Lebane is implementing the *Handicraft Workshop project*, which includes training for people with disabilities and the production of traditional handicrafts. The Centre for Household Economics "*Danica Vuksanović*" from Leskovac organizes the event "*Golden Hands*". Local branches of the National Employment Service conduct various programs and training sessions for unemployed women. Notably, there is a training program for traditional crafts in Lebane, supported by the women's association "Ruža", known for its expertise in knitting, crocheting, embroidery, and other handicrafts. Founded in 2010, this association has around 40 women from the region involved in these crafts.

The area of Jablanica and Pcinja Districts, encompassing mountains along with other settlements, objects, and natural and cultural landmarks. However, the potential for development has not been fully utilized. The most significant existing tourist capacities are in spa and health-recreational tourism. In the municipality of Medveđa, where tourism is a cornerstone of overall economic development, the main tourist activities are centred around the Institute for Specialized Rehabilitation in Sijarinska Banja, which has approximately 300 beds (150 in the institute's stationary facility, Hotel "Gejzer," a B-category establishment with 100 beds, and the "Sijarinska Banja" camp with 50 beds). The spa itself has about 1500 beds in the private sector. In the municipality of Bujanovac, the driver of tourist development is the Holding company DP "Vrelo," which includes the "Vrelo" Institute - a B-category facility with 200 beds in Bujanovačka Banja and the accommodation at the monastery of St. Prohor Pčinjski with 100 beds. The company employs around 200 workers. In Bujanovac, hospitality services are also provided by DP "Proleće," which includes Motel Kamp Bujanovac with 80 beds and a facility for the production of hospitality equipment, employing 52 workers. Within DP "Duvanska industrija" Bujanovac operates a lakeside motel with 25 beds. There are no tourism and hospitality enterprises (legal entities) in the municipality of Preševo. Registered tourist traffic in this municipality pertains to private hospitality businesses.

4.4 Institutional setting

The districts of Jablanica and Pčinja encompass 13 local governments, which serve as the primary institutions for delivering public services (the Law on Local Self-Government, *Zakon o lokalnoj samouprava*, 2007). All Serbian municipalities, regardless of size, have identical responsibilities (Anđelković Đoković, 2024). This means that citizens of both Crna Trava, the smallest municipality, and Leskovac, the largest city in the districts, are entitled to provide the same 2,000 services (Anđelković Đoković, 2024). These include maintaining civil registries, processing maternity leave compensation, issuing building permits, land rezoning, and environmental assessments.

Additionally, public services are also provided by the national level institutions that have their branches at the local level. For example, there are: Police Departments, Postal Services, Employment Offices, Health Centres, Social Health Insurance, Centres for Social Work etc.

The **network of healthcare institutions** is prescribed by the Regulation on the plan of the network of healthcare institutions in Serbia (*Uredba o planu mreže zdravstvenih ustanova Srbije*, 2020). Healthcare institutions are managed from the national level by the Ministry of Health. Up to 2020 healthcare institutions were owned by the local government but having in mind the low capacities of the LSGs and their low budgets Ministry of Health decided to transfer the ownership to the national level. This Regulation prescribes that in Jablanica district there are 8 health institutions: 1 pharmacy, 4 primary healthcare centers, 1 health center containing both primary health center and general hospital within itself, 1 specialized hospital and 1 public health institute. In the Pčinja district there are 12 healthcare institutions: 2 pharmacies, 5 primary healthcare centers, 2 healthcare centers containing primary and secondary healthcare, 2 specialized hospitals and 1 public health institute. Therefore, in the Jablanica and Pčinja districts there is representation of primary and secondary healthcare institutions, but there are not tertiary healthcare institutions – therefore citizens of these districts are redirected to the University Clinical Center in the City of Niš. The network of primary healthcare facilities in rural areas is relatively dispersed, comprising 35 health stations.

The education system is managed by the LSGs as their basic jurisdiction. In the school 2022/2023 year, based on the Statistical Office data, primary education in the Jablanica District was organized in 43 eight-year primary schools and 18 secondary schools, with 5 specialized schools and 6 adult education schools. There is one faculty. The Pčinja District has 45 primary schools, 18 secondary schools, 2 specialized schools, 2 adult education schools, one faculty.

As for the **labor market support**, the National Employment Service in the Jablanica and Pčinj districts has two branches (Vranje and Leskovac) as well as 6 offices (Bojnik, Vlasotince, Lebane, Medvedja, Vladičin Han and Bujanovac). In these branches/offices, unemployed persons can receive support in employment, attend training, access employment counselors, etc. In those municipalities where there are no NES services, the unemployed can receive services on the premises of LSG. (retrieved from the NES website, January 19th).

4.5 Local policies and instruments

The **Law on the Planning System in Serbia** (Zakon o planskom sistemu, 2018) regulates, among other things, the process of preparing, adopting, and implementing all public policies, as well as ensuring the mutual alignment of policies in the Republic of Serbia at all levels of government (national, provincial, and local). Public policies include strategies, programs, policy concepts, and action plans.

At the local level, public policies can include policies such as:

- the Medium-Term Development Strategy of Local Self-Government,
- the Sustainable Development Strategy of Local Self-Government,
- the Employment Strategy and Action Plans on local level,
- the Urban Area Development Strategy,
- the Smart Cities Development Strategy etc.

All 13 LSGs from the Jablanica and Pčinja district can adopt above mentioned public policies. All of them in some part can influence rural development. Below we present the public policies of Leskovac and Vranje as the two biggest cities in these districts.

The city of Leskovac has two mid-term active strategies presented below. All other strategic documents such as Local Employment Action Plan Of The City Of Leskovac 2024-2026 (Lokalni akcioni plan zapošljavanja 2024-2026), Urban plans, Program for agricultural and rural development support (Program podrške za sprovođenje poljoprivredne politike i politike ruralnog razvoja 2024) emerged from these documents as "shorter-term" measures for the implementation of strategic decisions.

- **Medium-Term Plan Of The City Of Leskovac From 2024 to 2026** (Srednjoročni plan rasta Grada Leskovca od 2024. do 2026.)

The medium-term development plan includes, among other things, measures aimed at fostering rural development directly or indirectly, such as expanding the water supply and sewage networks, supporting investments and employment through subsidies for self-employment, public works, and internships, establishing a Start-up and reconstructing the Youth Center in Leskovac. Additional initiatives include supporting the restoration of religious sites to boost tourism, providing agricultural subsidies, assisting cooperatives and other farmer associations in protecting cultural heritage and geographical origin, and improving rural infrastructure, including local roads and community centers.

- **Leskovac Development Plan For The Period 2023 – 2029** (Plan razvoja Grada Leskovca za period 2023-2029)

The Development Plan for the City of Leskovac outlines three key development directions: economic, social, and territorial development with environmental protection. Within economic development, rural tourism and agricultural advancements are emphasized as vital opportunities. Initiatives include supporting rural tourism infrastructure, fostering rural youth

self-employment through cooperatives, organizing training for rural accommodation, and enhancing cultural routes. Investments also target agricultural modernization, infrastructure, and promoting organic and geographically indicated products. Specific measures include restoring traditional mills and creating thematic cultural experiences to bolster tourism and sustainable local economic growth.

The city of Vranje has two mid-term strategic documents presented below. All other strategic documents emerged from these documents as shorter-term measures for implementation of these strategic decisions. These strategic documents are e.g. Strategy for Youth Support, Local Employment Action Plan, Local action plan for the social inclusion of Roma men and women in the territory of the City of Vranje etc.

- **Medium-Term Plan Of The City Of Vranje From 2023 to 2025** (Srednjoročni plan rasta Grada Vranja od 2023. do 2025.)

The Medium-Term Development Plan for the City of Vranje includes measures directly or indirectly supporting rural development. These measures involve building bridges, roads, and other infrastructure in rural areas, promoting self-employment and employment through training and subsidies, supporting ethno-tourism and categorizing hospitality and accommodation capacities in rural regions, and developing strategic documents to enhance agricultural support. These initiatives aim to improve living conditions, promote tourism, and support sustainable economic growth in rural communities.

- **Vranje Development Plan For The Period 2021 – 2030** (Plan razvoja Grada Leskovca za period 2021-2030)

The Development Plan for the City of Vranje highlights key priorities for agriculture and rural development, emphasizing improved rural infrastructure to address depopulation trends. This includes constructing roads, expanding water supply networks, and improving ICT, energy, and social infrastructure. Agricultural initiatives focus on modernizing production, supporting organic farming, livestock development, diversification, and creating measures to encourage youth to remain in rural areas. Additionally, the plan promotes linking primary agriculture with the food industry, ensuring sustainable, efficient, and profitable agricultural production while safeguarding environmental and biological resources.

5. Vulnerability and Social Exclusion in the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts

The basic theoretical and practical understanding of social exclusion in the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts was formed based on interviews with representatives of local municipalities and local CSOs. The fields of action and interests of these organizations are very diverse and cover almost all spheres of life: protecting the rights of socially vulnerable population groups, including marginalized groups, public advocacy, promoting youth and sports development, promoting traditional and cultural values, supporting poverty reduction, promoting international cooperation and solidarity, developing science and culture, supporting entrepreneurship development, promoting a multi-ethnic community and culture, sustainable management of natural resources, and the development of hunting, beekeeping, agriculture, environmental protection, and ecological activities.

Civil sector representatives express high levels of dissatisfaction regarding the socio-economic situation in the region, particularly in its rural areas. They identify the most significant problems as the depopulation of rural areas and the exodus of the younger population due to extremely poor living conditions and lack of employment opportunities. Smaller municipalities in the region lack active industries, entrepreneurship is very underdeveloped, and the unemployment rate is high. They cite complicated administration and lack of personal funds for investments as reasons for the lack of entrepreneurship. Insufficient funds also result in poor marketing, making market entry for entrepreneurs from these areas very difficult. Despite all the mentioned problems, the civil sector sees certain potential in this region, such as its still-preserved environment and rich tradition and cultural heritage.

5.1 Social exclusion and poverty

According to official poverty and social exclusion data in Serbia, the at-risk-of-poverty rate reached 20.1% overall in 2022 with notable disparities among demographic groups. Among individuals aged 65 and over, women face a significantly higher risk (25.3%) compared to men (21.2%), and a similar trend is evident for individuals aged 55–64 (women: 20.9%, men: 25.4%). Social exclusion is also pronounced among single-person households, particularly those aged 65 and older (34.2%), while households with three or more children report a 34.7% exclusion rate (Statistical Office, 2022). Official data for social exclusion and risk of poverty is not available at the regional or LSG level. However, based on the data regarding the type of households social exclusion could be indicative. For example, in the South and East Serbia region, 144,548 out of 524,574 households are single-person, while the majority consist of two members (146,312). The high prevalence of smaller households, coupled with the aging population, underscores the vulnerability of these groups to poverty and exclusion, highlighting the need for targeted interventions in this region.

Estimations for the LSG level were made for the 2011 data. Even though the data is not up-to-date conclusions could be indicative. In 2011, the poverty risk rate in Serbia was 25.7% nationally, while the South and East Serbia region faced a significantly higher rate of 33%. The Jablanica District holds the

highest poverty rate in Serbia, at 45.5%, followed closely by the Pčinja District at 42%. These alarming figures highlight the deep socioeconomic challenges in the South and East Serbia region, particularly in rural and underdeveloped municipalities.

Figure 2. Map of Social Exclusion based on Poverty Rates, 2011

Source: Republički zavod za statistiku & Svetska banka. (2016). *Mapa siromaštva u Srbiji*. Beograd: Republički zavod za statistiku, uz podršku Tima za socijalno uključivanje i smanjenje siromaštva Vlade Republike Srbije.

According to the *Regional Strategy for Rural Development of the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts* (Centre for the Development of Jablanica and Pčinja Districts, 2013.), in 2011, 43% of households in the region are classified as vulnerable. This group includes households below average, poor, elderly, and single-person households. Most rural households assess their living standard as average. However, 40% of households report that their living standard is poor or very poor, while only 10% consider their situation to be better than average. Households with decision-makers over the age of 50 are more likely to have a negative view of their current situation and future prospects over the next five years. They perceive themselves as less competitive compared to the urban labour force with reduced opportunities for the economic exploitation of their knowledge and skills. This makes the rural population more dependent on unstable and insufficient agricultural production income under extreme market instability. A lack of financial resources and markets ranks high among the

developmental constraints, reflecting a lack of recognition of business and social partners in their immediate surroundings. Almost half of the surveyed households (46%) view agriculture as a potential for future development. Employment outside agriculture represents a possibility for progress for 33% of the surveyed households. Households do not recognize their own responsibility for their current position nor their ability to improve their situation in the future. They believe that higher levels of decision-making and responsibility (local government and state) are more responsible for their situation than they or their immediate environment (cooperatives, NGOs, business sector). Residents are generally dissatisfied with the quality of life in their communities.

5.2 Labour market

Observing the data from the Labour Force Survey, only comparable at the international level, only data at the level of regions are available. Although the data from Jablanica and Pčinja is not available, analysis of region data can be indicative. As mentioned, Jablanica and Pčinja Districts are an integral part of Southern and Eastern Serbia region. According to the Labor Force Survey data for the third quarter of 2023 (Statistical Office, 2023) the **activity rate** for the population aged 15 and over was 55.8% in Serbia. By region, the highest activity rate was recorded in the Belgrade region at 60.1%, while the lowest was in the Southern and Eastern Serbia region at 51.9%.

The **employment rate** for the population aged 15 and over in the third quarter of 2023 was 50.7% in Serbia (Statistical Office, Labour Force Survey, Q3 2023). The Southern and Eastern Serbia region had the lowest employment rate at 46%, which is 10 percentage points lower than the Belgrade region.

The **unemployment rate** for the population aged 15 and over was 9% in Serbia. Regionally, a slightly higher unemployment rate of 11.4% was recorded in the Southern and Eastern Serbia region, which is five percentage points higher than the unemployment rate in the Belgrade region (Statistical Office, Labour Force Survey, Q3 2023).

However, the data could be analysed on local level if we use registered employment and unemployment data. This data is not methodologically comparable with internationally accepted statistics because they use administrative databases and not a labour force survey as a source, but it could be indicative.

The data reveals that the Jablanica and Pčinja districts experience relatively high unemployment rates (14%) and low employment rates 27%, suggesting a significant portion of the population remains out of work. The average net wage of 55,025 RSD (470 EUR) is below the national average, reflecting economic challenges in these regions.

At the level of LSGs, two most challenging municipalities in terms of employment are Bujanovac and Preševo, with the lowest registered employment rates (13% and 12%, respectively) and relatively low average wages, indicating a need for increased job opportunities. On the other hand, Crna Trava and Medveđa show the best outcomes with high employment rates (76% and 29%) and relatively higher average wages. However, we need to know that these are very small LSGs (e.g. Crna Trava has around 1,000 citizens) that influenced the high share of employment.

Table 5: Labour market indicators, 2022

LSG	Registered employment per capita 2022	Registered unemployment per capita 2022	Average net wage RSD	Average net wage EUR
Leskovac	30%	10%	57468	491
Bojnik	16%	17%	49706	425
Vlasotince	28%	13%	52009	445
Lebane	16%	18%	52611	450
Medveđa	29%	14%	62230	532
Crna Trava	76%	13%	52380	448
Vranje	28%	8%	59025	504
Bosilegrad	23%	23%	52720	451
Bujanovac	13%	10%	52354	447
Vladičin Han	27%	11%	58962	504
Preševo	12%	12%	50627	433
Surdulica	26%	11%	58912	504
Trgovište	26%	21%	56328	481

Source: Official Statistics, 2022, Registered employment and unemployment

5.3 Environmental vulnerability

Based on the Regional Strategy for Rural Development of the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts (2013), the environmental vulnerability and risk of natural disasters in the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts are influenced by both natural and anthropogenic factors. The intensity of seismic hazards over a 100-year return period varies. The northern part of the region (from the Medveđa – Crna Trava line) is encompassed by isoseists ranging from 6.5^o to 7^o MCS. South of this line, the intensity increases to 7-8^o MCS, and around Vranje and Bujanovac, and west of Preševo towards Gnjilane, it approaches 9^o MCS.

Ionizing radiation of natural and artificial genesis is not significantly pronounced, except at certain locations contaminated by depleted uranium ammunition during the NATO bombing in 1999 (locations: Borivac 1 and 2 and Bratoselice in the municipality of Bujanovac, Pljačkovica in the

municipality of Vranje, and Reljan in the municipality of Preševo). Partial decontamination was carried out only in the municipality of Bujanovac, where it is estimated that 10% of the ammunition was removed from the affected locations.

The considered area is one of the most endangered in Serbia in terms of the development of erosive and torrential processes in catchments. Uncontrolled forest exploitation, especially in the municipalities of Preševo, Bujanovac, and Medveđa, has further intensified already developed erosion processes. The soil in the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts is degraded due to activities of heating plants, unplanned and uncontrolled exploitation of mineral raw materials (soil damage by pits, tailings accumulations), landslides, and erosion. The area also experiences soil pollution around mines, mostly with sulphur compounds, hydrocarbons, etc. A particular problem is the unsanitary, illegal dumpsites that contaminate the soil. Issues also include irrational use of fertile agricultural land, uncontrolled and excessive use of agrochemical agents, irrational use of pesticides and artificial fertilizers, lack of a soil quality monitoring system, etc. Soil is also threatened by unregulated and untreated wastewater, as well as through air pollution (mostly from the surrounding areas).

5.4 Disadvantaged groups

Based on the analysis provided above we disadvantaged groups in Jablanica and Pčinja are:

5.4.1 Youth in NEET status

One of the primary drivers of the NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) status among young people is a lack of access to quality education and training programs. In many regions, especially rural or underdeveloped areas, educational institutions are either insufficiently equipped or entirely absent.

To address the lack of access to quality education and training programs for young people, a crucial strategy involves the development and expansion of vocational training and retraining programs. By partnering with local businesses and industries, these programs can be tailored to meet current labour market demands, providing relevant and practical skills. The Draft of National Program for Social Entrepreneurship Support emphasizes the importance of raising awareness among young people regarding the social entrepreneurship as possible profession for the future.

5.4.2 Women

One of the main causes of social exclusion among women is limited access to the labour market and rigid gender roles. In many communities, especially in rural or underdeveloped areas, young women face discrimination in employment and restricted opportunities for professional development. Traditional gender roles often impose expectations that young women take primary responsibility for household and family care, preventing them from engaging in educational and professional activities. Additionally, the lack of support for balancing work and family obligations, such as childcare services and flexible working hours, further contributes to the social exclusion of young women from the labour market and educational programs. These factors together make it difficult for young women to acquire the relevant skills and qualifications needed for a successful career.

A social inclusion strategy for young women should address barriers to education and employment while challenging traditional gender roles. Increasing employment opportunities can be achieved by connecting women's entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurship, and innovative forms of economic cooperation that create job opportunities for women. Empowerment programs should build leadership and entrepreneurial skills and support women's networks.

5.4.3 Entrepreneurs

One of the primary drivers of social inclusion for entrepreneurs is access to supportive networks and resources. Entrepreneurs face challenges such as limited access to funding, mentorship, and markets, which can hinder their growth and development. Creating an ecosystem that fosters innovation and collaboration is essential. This includes providing access to business incubators, accelerators, and coworking spaces that offer mentorship, training, and networking opportunities. Additionally, policies that encourage entrepreneurship, such as tax incentives, grants, and simplified regulatory frameworks, can significantly boost entrepreneurial activity.

A social inclusion strategy for entrepreneurs should prioritize equitable access to resources, networks, and opportunities. This includes ensuring access to funding, technical assistance, and capacity-building support tailored to the needs of underrepresented groups. Establishing supportive networks of mentors, peers, and advisors is essential for guidance and collaboration. Capacity-building programs should offer training in key entrepreneurial skills while facilitating access to markets through market research and partnership opportunities. These activities could be performed within the business incubators as a platform. Or some already existing platform could be used such as the Networks of SMEs, Business Chamber of Serbia capacities etc. Advocating for policies that remove barriers to entry and promote diversity in entrepreneurship is crucial. Additionally, fostering a culture of innovation and collaboration through initiatives like innovation hubs and technology clusters can further support inclusive entrepreneurship.

5.4.4 Roma people

One of the primary drivers of social inclusion for Roma people in the Jablanica and Pčinja districts is access to education and vocational training. In many Roma communities, especially in underdeveloped or marginalized areas, there is a significant gap in educational attainment, which hinders their ability to access stable employment and participate fully in society. Cultural barriers and socio-economic disadvantages often result in lower school enrolment rates and higher dropout rates among Roma children, limiting their opportunities for personal and professional development. Additionally, the lack of targeted programs and support services to address the specific needs of the Roma population, such as language barriers and discrimination, further exacerbates their social exclusion. These challenges make it difficult for Roma individuals to gain the necessary skills and qualifications to secure meaningful employment and improve their socio-economic status.

A social inclusion strategy for Roma people in the Jablanica and Pčinja districts should focus on improving access to education and vocational training while addressing the cultural and socio-economic barriers they face. Enhancing educational opportunities can be achieved by implementing

targeted programs that support Roma children's enrolment and retention in schools, such as scholarships, mentorship, and after-school tutoring. Vocational training tailored to the needs of the Roma community, along with initiatives that promote adult education, can help equip Roma individuals with the skills needed for stable employment.

Empowerment programs should focus on building leadership and professional skills within the Roma community, encouraging participation in local decision-making processes, and fostering connections with broader social networks. Additionally, promoting social entrepreneurship and cooperative models that align with Roma cultural values can create sustainable job opportunities and pathways out of poverty. Addressing discrimination and ensuring the availability of support services, such as language assistance and anti-discrimination training, are essential components of this strategy, helping to create an inclusive environment where Roma people can fully participate in society.

5.5 Access to services

Based on the survey conducted by the Centre for Jablanica and Pčinja development in 2013, there is evident dissatisfaction with the availability and quality of rural services, especially healthcare services and cultural life in the village. Dissatisfaction with communal problems is considerably greater than with available services. Most households are aware of current agricultural policy measures, but a significantly smaller percentage has utilized these programs. The most commonly utilized measures are subsidies for mineral fertilizers and fuel and milk premiums. Insufficient information, difficult access to advisory services, low levels of initiative, and the absence of administrative local capacities are major constraints to more active utilization of state support funds. Despite acknowledging that a lack of money is their main developmental constraint and needing information on financial aid, most of the rural households have never attempted to obtain a loan.

There are certain services that are well-developed based on this survey, such as primary schools, shops, local offices, and playgrounds. However, in places where these institutions and services are available, there is some dissatisfaction with the quality of services and their organization. The greatest dissatisfaction is related to the availability of healthcare services and cultural life in the village. Throughout the region, there is a problem of a lack of expert assistance in agricultural production. The economic position of minorities, the refugee population, and pronounced rural poverty make the region very sensitive.

6. Assets and potentials in the region

In collaboration with representatives from 13 municipalities, the main fields of developmental potential and social infrastructure for the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts have been established. These potentials include:

Development of Agribusiness: Representatives of local governments see opportunities for improving agribusiness through the establishment and support of existing small and medium-sized enterprises, with a focus on those engaged in the processing of agricultural products, refinement and marketing of forest fruits and medicinal herbs, and organic production. A significant problem is the lack of adequate

information and data on market demands and the adaptation of production to these demands. Adding value to agricultural products through standardization and certification is missing across the entire region. Market research would contribute to recognizing the necessity of introducing standards and certifications in production, processing, and service provision. Local representatives consider many branches of agriculture significant for the region's development, including livestock farming, beekeeping, viticulture, fruit growing, vegetable growing, and the collection of forest fruits and medicinal herbs.

Industry development: The municipalities of the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts lack a proper assessment of industrial capacities and potential for new development, which impedes the creation of a comprehensive development and expansion plan. Improving traffic infrastructure is essential for industrial development, necessitating the renovation of existing roads and the construction of new ones. The enhancement and restoration of airports in Niš and Leskovac are also deemed crucial for attracting investors. Underdeveloped municipalities in this region (e.g., Crna Trava, Medveđa, Lebane, Trgovište) have significant potential in the form of brownfield locations that can be offered to investors under favourable conditions, with the obligation of employing residents.

Tourism and Services development: The entire area is rich in diverse natural and cultural assets that are insufficiently economically valorised. The first step in valorising available resources through tourism development is creating an action plan for the entire region, aligning the activities and goals of all 13 municipalities, and setting priorities. The region hosts numerous events of international and regional significance, which represent a substantial tourism potential but are not sufficiently utilized to improve life in rural areas.

Multifunctionality of the rural economy: Local government representatives see opportunities for diversifying the rural economy by supporting small rural households and their networking. Creating functional cooperation among households involved in production, processing, and service provision (in tourism) and their joint market presence is the only way to improve the quality of life in the villages of this District. Traditional crafts, souvenir production, marketing of forest fruits and medicinal herbs, as well as seasonal work, are recognized as primary sources of diversification.

Infrastructure development: Local governments believe it is necessary to create a priority list for infrastructure renovation and construction across the entire District to use limited financial resources more effectively. Besides transportation and utility infrastructure, which needs renovation in all municipalities, the adaptation of storage capacities and the construction of business incubator centres are identified as very important.

Attractiveness for investors and financing: According to local government representatives, the biggest obstacle to attracting investors to the municipalities of this District is the cumbersome and slow administration. Natural and cultural resources, proximity to Corridor 10, cheap labour, and the region's strategic location for cross-border activities provide a good basis for investments. The local community underutilises funds from various sources available to this region due to a lack of good and purposeful ideas. Commonly available funds include self-employment programs (National Employment Service and Development Fund), subsidies from the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management,

the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy, the Office for Sustainable Development of Underdeveloped Municipalities, as well as European Union and other international organization funds (e.g., USAID). Although there are individual examples of drawing funds from various donors, the general awareness among the population about these opportunities is low.

Social services: Local governments believe it is necessary to align education programs throughout the district with labour market needs. Vocational schools should be prioritized, and their profiling should be based on industry feedback. The rural school network must be improved and more rationally organized, given the declining number of school-age children in villages. The healthcare of rural populations would be significantly improved by well-organized and supported mobile medical teams regularly visiting the most remote parts of the municipalities.

Civil sector and cooperation: Local governments consider the civil sector as their "extended arm" but see the need for better organization and a higher level of activity within the non-governmental sector. Citizen associations are not few in this area, but more communication with local governments and joint activity planning is necessary. The Jablanica and Pcinja Districts have a very favourable position for cooperation with neighbouring countries (Bulgaria, and Macedonia), making various sources of financial support (cross-border cooperation) available for this purpose. Local governments see cross-border cooperation primarily through exchanging experiences, knowledge, and best practices, as well as establishing joint distribution centres for agricultural products and services. Besides cooperation with neighbouring countries, there are significant opportunities for inter-municipal cooperation within the region, particularly in enhancing market placement (branding the region, joint ventures) and environmental protection (regional landfill, afforestation, wastewater treatment).

Information dissemination: Cities in this District have a good system for disseminating information about their activities and available support through websites, local media, and promotional materials. However, underdeveloped municipalities lack their own websites, and local media are often inactive (e.g., Crna Trava, Lebane, Medvedja, Trgoviste). Agricultural producers in all municipalities have access to the Rural Development Support Network offices of the Ministry of Agriculture, which provide information on financial and non-financial support from this ministry.

6.1 Significance of developing the socio-economic potentials in the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts

The strategic development of agribusiness, industry, tourism, and the rural economy in the Jablanica and Pcinja regions is pivotal for fostering economic diversification and growth. Diversifying the economic base reduces dependency on a singular sector, thereby mitigating the risks associated with economic volatility, ensuring a more resilient economic structure capable of withstanding external shocks and promoting sustainable long-term growth. The integration of various sectors creates a robust economic ecosystem, enhancing regional stability and prosperity.

One of the most critical impacts of developmental initiatives is the **creation of employment opportunities**. By focusing on agribusiness, industrial development, and tourism, the regions can generate a significant number of jobs. This is particularly crucial for rural areas suffering from high

unemployment rates and youth migration. Employment in these sectors will not only retain the local workforce but also attract skilled professionals, contributing to the overall socio-economic upliftment of the regions

Improving infrastructure and industrial capacities, along with making the region more attractive for investors, is essential for stimulating economic growth. Investments, both domestic and foreign, can lead to the establishment of new enterprises and the expansion of existing ones, thus injecting capital into the local economy. Enhanced infrastructure, such as upgraded transportation networks and business incubators, provides the necessary support for business operations, making the regions more competitive and appealing to investors.

Development in social services, including education, healthcare, and the civil sector, directly translates to an improved quality of life for residents. Aligning educational programs with market needs ensures that the workforce is adequately skilled, while improved healthcare services guarantee better health outcomes. Furthermore, strengthening the civil sector enhances community engagement and social cohesion, fostering a more inclusive society. Mobile medical teams and rationalized rural school networks are examples of targeted interventions that address specific local needs, thereby enhancing overall well-being.

The region's rich **natural and cultural heritage** offers significant untapped potential for economic development, particularly through tourism and agribusiness. Properly leveraging these resources not only generates revenue but also promotes conservation and appreciation of local heritage. Developing tourism infrastructure and creating comprehensive action plans for the regions can transform these assets into sustainable economic drivers, benefiting both the local communities and the broader economy.

Robust infrastructure is the backbone of economic development. Upgrading transportation, utilities, and storage facilities, along with establishing business incubators, creates an environment conducive to business growth and operational efficiency. These improvements are essential for supporting the expansion of industrial and agribusiness activities, facilitating smoother logistics, and enhancing overall productivity.

Standardization and certification of agricultural products, combined with comprehensive market research, are vital for enhancing the competitiveness of local products. This approach ensures that products meet quality standards required by both domestic and international markets, thus increasing their marketability. Supporting small and medium-sized enterprises in adopting these standards can significantly boost their competitiveness, leading to increased market share and economic gains.

Environmental conservation is an integral aspect of sustainable development. Initiatives such as afforestation, wastewater treatment, and the creation of regional landfills are crucial for maintaining environmental health. Sustainable practices in agriculture, industry, and tourism ensure that economic development does not come at the expense of environmental degradation. These efforts can contribute to long-term ecological balance, ensuring that natural resources are preserved for future generations.

In conclusion, the strategic development of socio-economic potentials in the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts is crucial for driving comprehensive economic growth, improving quality of life, attracting investments, and promoting environmental sustainability.

7. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP

Conducting a socio-economic study has proven to be crucial for comprehensively understanding the practical challenges faced by marginalized groups in the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts. The study provided a structured and detailed assessment of the socio-economic conditions in these regions, which was essential for developing effective and targeted interventions. Through the study, we thoroughly examined the current state of economic activity, employment rates, and income levels among marginalized groups. By identifying specific socio-economic conditions such as high unemployment rates, low levels of educational attainment, and limited access to essential services, we revealed the underlying factors contributing to the marginalization of these communities. The study also uncovered unique barriers and obstacles faced by these groups, including geographical isolation, inadequate infrastructure, and limited economic opportunities. This in-depth understanding of localized issues will be instrumental in crafting policies and programs that address the specific needs of the communities in Jablanica and Pcinja, moving beyond broad, one-size-fits-all solutions.

In addition, the study facilitated crucial stakeholder engagement by providing a clear and objective basis for dialogue among policymakers, community leaders, and the marginalized groups themselves. Through these discussions, we built a shared understanding of the issues at hand and fostered collaborative efforts to address the root causes of marginalization and inequality. This engagement was key to building social capital and creating a foundation for future partnerships and initiatives aimed at achieving long-term, sustainable improvements in the well-being of residents in these districts.

The development of the whole region includes enhancing the agribusiness sector by supporting small and medium-sized enterprises focused on the processing and marketing of agricultural products, forest fruits, medicinal herbs, and organic produce. Strengthening industrial capacities requires an assessment of current assets and the development of infrastructure, such as roads and airports, to attract investors. Tourism can be promoted through the economic valorization of the region's diverse natural and cultural heritage. Additionally, diversifying the rural economy by supporting small household businesses and traditional crafts can create new income streams and improve the quality of life in rural areas.

In Serbia, the implementation of the Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) is focused on forming a network of partners to identify effective practices in the process of strengthening the socio-economic position of young people not in employment, education, or training (NEET), women, and entrepreneurs. Theoretical insights and practical experiences of the respondents indicate that these categories are underrepresented in the labor market and marginalized in the social structure. A collaborative approach is crucial for strengthening the socioeconomic position of marginalized groups, contributing to their social inclusion, and improving societal conditions.

The primary conclusion of the MAP meetings emphasized the critical importance of cooperation among all actors in empowering marginalized groups. By working together, local innovative initiatives can help reduce unemployment and poverty risk rates, while increasing labor market participation. The next steps will involve the Institute for Development and Innovation working closely with local

governments, civil society organizations, the business community, and individuals, all coordinated by the Center for the Development of the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts. Coordinated effort aims to create an inclusive and supportive environment where local communities can thrive and contribute to the overall socio-economic development of the regions. Through the collective endeavor of all stakeholders, the regions can achieve sustainable growth and development, ensuring long-term prosperity and well-being for their inhabitants.

8. References

- Anđelković Đoković, M. (2024). Finalna analiza: Monitoring projekata i usluga podržanih kroz fond za MOS sa pregledom strukture finalnih korisnika gde je to primenljivo [Final analysis: Monitoring of projects and services supported through the MOS fund with an overview of the structure of final beneficiaries where applicable]. Izveštaj pripremljen za Ministarstvo državne uprave i lokalne samouprave Republike Srbije u okviru projekta Lokalna samouprava za 21. vek, uz podršku Vlade Švajcarske.
- Cvejić, S, Babović, M. i Vuković, O. (2008) Mapiranje socijalnih preduzeća u Srbiji, Beograd: UNDP.
- Ministry of Economy. (2022). Report on small and medium-sized enterprises and entrepreneurship 2020. Ministry of Economy.
- Ministry of Labor, Employment, Veteran and Social Affairs. (2024). Draft Program for Supporting the Development of Social Entrepreneurship.
- Mitić, T. (2024). Nacionalna strategija ravnomernog regionalnog razvoja Srbije iz perspektive decentralizacije: Praktična politika, analiza, predlog nacrtu plana razvoja Srbije [National Strategy for Balanced Regional Development of Serbia from the Perspective of Decentralization: Practical Policy, Analysis, and Draft Development Plan Proposal]. Nacionalna koalicija za decentralizaciju.
- NALED (2024). Social enterprises for state support. Retrieved December 5, 2024, from <https://naled.rs/en/vest-registracija-socijalnih-preduzeca-preduslov-za-podrsku-drzave-8776>
- NALED. (2025). Siva knjiga 17. Belgrade, Serbia: National Alliance for Local Economic Development (NALED).
- Regional Strategy for Rural Development of the Jablanica and Pčinja Districts (2013). Centre for the Development of Jablanica and Pcinja Districts.
- Republički zavod za statistiku & Svetska banka. (2016). Mapa siromaštva u Srbiji. Beograd: Republički zavod za statistiku, uz podršku Tima za socijalno uključivanje i smanjenje siromaštva Vlade Republike Srbije.
- Tešić, S., & Radetić, G. (2023). Socijalno preduzetništvo kao potencijal za razvoj odgovornih i održivih ženskih inicijativa. Agencija Ujedinjenih nacija za rodnu ravnopravnost i osnaživanje žena.
- Vukmirović, D. (2014). Economic impact of social enterprises in the Republic of Serbia. Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia
- Analyzed regulatory and strategic framework:
- Constitution of the Republic of Serbia (2006). Ustav Republike Srbije.
- Law on Agriculture and Rural Development (2009). Zakon o poljoprivredi i ruralnom razvoju.
- Law on Associations (2009). Zakon o udruženjima.
- Law on Cooperatives (2015). Zakon o zadrugama.
- Law on Endowments and Foundations (2010). Zakon o fondacijama i zadužbinama.
- Law on Regional Development (2009). Zakon o ravnomernom regionalnom razvoju.
- Law on Social Entrepreneurship (2022). Zakon o socijalnom preduzetništvu.
- Law on State Administration (2005). Zakon o državnoj upravi.
- Law on Territorial Organization (2007). Zakon o teritorijalnoj organizaciji.

- Law on the Planning System in Serbia (2018). Zakon o planskom sistemu Srbije.
- Medium-Term Plan of the City of Leskovac 2024–2026. (2024). Srednjoročni plan rasta Grada Leskovca od 2024. do 2026.
- Medium-Term Plan of the City of Vranje 2023–2025. (2023). Srednjoročni plan rasta Grada Vranja od 2023. do 2025.
- Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Serbia. (2022). IPARD III Programme for the Republic of Serbia for the Period 2021 - 2027. January 2022.
- National Rural Development Program 2022–2024. (2022). Nacionalni program ruralnog razvoja 2022–2024.
- Regional Spatial Plan of the Municipalities of Southern Pomoravlje (2010). Regionalni prostorni plan opština Južnog Pomoravlja.
- Regulation on the Plan of the Network of Healthcare Institutions in Serbia (2020). Uredba o planu mreže zdravstvenih ustanova Srbije.
- Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development 2014–2024. (2014). Strategija poljoprivrede i ruralnog razvoja Republike Srbije za period 2014–2024.
- Strategy for Deinstitutionalization and Development of Community Social Protection Services (2022–2026). (2022). Strategija za deinstitutionalizaciju i razvoj usluga socijalne zaštite u zajednici za period 2022–2026.
- Strategy for Improving the Status of Persons with Disabilities 2020–2024. (2020). Strategija za poboljšanje statusa osoba sa invaliditetom za period 2020–2024.
- Strategy for Social Inclusion of Roma 2022–2030. (2022). Strategija za socijalno uključivanje Roma i Romkinja za period 2022–2030.
- Strategy for Sustainable Urban Development in Serbia 2019–2030. (2019). Strategija održivog urbanog razvoja Srbije do 2030. godine.
- Strategy for the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises (2023–2027). (2023). Strategija razvoja malih i srednjih preduzeća za period 2023–2027.
- Tourism Development Strategy of Serbia (2016–2025). (2016). Strategija razvoja turizma Republike Srbije 2016–2025.
- Development Plan for the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina 2023–2030. (2023). Plan razvoja AP Vojvodina 2023–2030.
- Development Plan of the City of Leskovac 2023–2029. (2023). Plan razvoja Grada Leskovca za period 2023–2029.
- Development Plan of the City of Vranje 2021–2030. (2021). Plan razvoja Grada Vranja za period 2021–2030.
- Development Strategy of Belgrade to 2027. (2027). Strategija razvoja Grada Beograda do 2027.
- Employment Strategy of the Republic of Serbia (2021–2026). (2021). Strategija zapošljavanja u Republici Srbiji za 2021–2026.

- Strategy for creating an enabling environment for the development of civil society in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2022–2030. (2022). Strategija za kreiranje povoljnog okruženja za razvoj civilnog sektora u Republici Srbiji za period 2022–2030

9. Partners

